

Synthesis and acid catalyzed hydrolysis of di-*m*-toluidine phosphate

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Abstract : Di-*m*-toluidine phosphate was synthesized by direct phosphorylation with POCl_3 of the parent compound. Kinetics of hydrolysis of di-*m*-toluidine phosphate was carried out in acid medium from 0.1 to 7.0 mol dm^{-3} in 40% dioxane-water (v/v) medium at 60 °C. Ionic strength data exhibit different contribution of neutral and conjugate acid species. Theoretical rates estimated from second empirical term of Debye-Hückel equation have been found in close agreement with experimental rates. A study of ionic strength, solvent, temperature and substrate effects have been carried out to determine the probable reaction paths. Molecularity and bond fission are also discussed in terms of Zucker-Hammett hypothesis, Bunnett and Bunnett-Olsen parameters and isokinetic relationship.

Keywords : Kinetics, hydrolysis, di-*m*-toluidine phosphate.

Introduction

Phosphate ester hydrolysis plays a very important role in energy metabolism and in various cellular signal transduction pathways in biological system¹. Much work has been done on the phosphate esters of C–O–P linkages, but kinetic study of phosphate esters having C–N–P linkages, known under the name of phosphoramides have received comparatively less attention, even though their significance as industrially important compounds has been recognized. They are used as pesticides², herbicides³, plasticizers⁴, flame retardants⁵, smoke generation⁶ and anticancer agents^{7,8}. Metallocomplexes of dithiophosphate diesters have been employed for many years as lubrication components in many applications including automobile engines⁹. Keeping this in view the kinetics of the hydrolysis of di-*m*-toluidine phosphate has been investigated. It is shown that, in the hydrolytic bond cleavage of diester the reaction proceed via neutral and conjugate acid species, depending upon the experimental conditions.

Experimental

Di-*m*-toluidine phosphate $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_2 \cdot (\text{CH}_3)_2 \cdot (\text{NH})_2 \cdot \text{PO}(\text{OH})$, molecular weight 276.0, was synthesized by the method of Rudert¹⁰. Reaction between *m*-toluidine and phosphorus oxychloride (2 : 1 M) gave crude diester as a solid. The crude product so obtained was recrystallized by ammonia and HCl to get pure sample. The observed melting point of diester is 130 °C. All the reac-

tions were carried out at the 60 ± 0.05 °C employing 5.0×10^{-4} M solution of the diester in 40% dioxane-water (v/v) medium. The constant ionic strengths were maintained by using mixtures of HCl and NaCl. The hydrolysis of di-*m*-toluidine phosphate was followed by spectrophotometric estimation of inorganic phosphate, using Allen's modified method¹¹. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The confirmation of compound was done by comparing theoretical and observed percentage of elements and by recording IR spectrum as shown below :

(a) Elemental analysis (%); theoretical (observed) : C, 60.8 (57.7); H, 6.1 (6.3); N, 10.1 (9.8).

(b) IR absorption spectra : The spectrum of di-*m*-toluidine phosphate was recorded by FTIR Model 136 Shimadzu. ν (KBr) (cm^{-1}) : 3387.11 (O–H); 3080.42 (N–H); 1558.54 (C=C); 1300.28 (P=O); 1619.09 (P–N–C).

Results and discussion

The hydrolysis of di-*m*-toluidine phosphate was carried out at 60 °C in the range of 0.1 to 7.0 mol dm^{-3} HCl in 40% dioxane-water (v/v) medium. In Table 1 the pseudo-first order rate constants are summarized, from which it is quite clear that the rate of reaction increases up to 5.0 mol dm^{-3} HCl but further increase in acid molarities decreases the rate¹² (Fig. 1).

The cause of bend has been attributed to the complete conversion of the ester molecule into their respective conju-

Table 1. Estimated and experimental rates of hydrolysis of di-*m*-toluidine phosphate at 60 °C

HCl (mol dm ⁻³)	$k_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)	$k_N \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)	$k \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)	$-\log (a_{H_2O})^n$	$k \times 10^3$ (min ⁻¹)		$4 + \log k$	
					Estd.	Expt.	Estd.	Expt.
0.1	0.38	5.45	5.83		5.83	4.32	1.77	1.64
0.2	0.78	5.45	6.23		6.23	5.86	1.79	1.77
0.5	2.04	5.45	7.49		7.49	7.16	1.87	1.85
1.0	4.52	5.45	9.97		9.97	8.92	1.99	1.95
2.0	10.99	5.45	16.44		16.44	15.72	2.22	2.20
3.0	19.95	5.45	25.40		25.40	25.94	2.40	2.41
						26.25 ^a		
						27.82 ^b		
4.0	32.36	5.45	37.81		37.81	36.70	2.58	2.56
5.0	48.98	5.45	54.43		54.43	55.22	2.74	2.74
						56.44 ^a		
						58.37 ^b		
6.0	72.44	5.45	77.89	(0.211) ²	33.87	31.65	2.53	2.50
7.0	102.32	5.45	107.77	(0.279) ³	20.24	19.83	2.31	2.30

^a50% dioxane, ^b60% dioxane.

Fig. 1. Acid log rate profile for the hydrolysis of di-*m*-toluidine phosphate at 60 °C.

gate acid species with the lowering of concentration of a nucleophile (water) which plays its role in rate determining step of bimolecular hydrolytic reaction.

Hydrolysis at constant ionic strength (1.0, 2.0 and 3.0 μ) shows that the reaction proceeds via both neutral and conjugate acid species. A plot of rate coefficients against acidity is linear for each ionic strength (Fig. 2). The linearity of the plot with positive slope represents the acid catalyzed reaction and since the slope of the linear plots increases with the increase in ionic strength, the hydrolysis via conjugate acid species exhibits positive salt effect. As all the lines meet at a point on the rate axis, the contribution to the overall reaction by the hydrolysis via neutral species is constant ($k_N = 5.45 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$) and is independent of ionic strength.

Fig. 2. Acid catalyzed hydrolysis of di-*m*-toluidine phosphate at constant ionic strength at 60 °C.

From the study of ionic strength effect, the total rates contributed by conjugate acid and neutral species can be calculated by the following 2nd empirical term of Debye-Hückel¹³ equation :

$$k = k_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} + k_N \quad (1)$$

In the above equation the terms k , k_{H^+} and k_N are experimental rate constants, the specific acid catalyzed and specific neutral rates at that ionic strength respectively. Specific acid catalyzed rates (k_{H^+}) were then converted in to acid rates ($k_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+}$) as :

$$k_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} = k_{H_0^+} \cdot C_{H^+} \exp b'_{H^+} \cdot \mu \quad (2)$$

where for HCl, μ and C_{H^+} are of the same value. The

Table 2. Arrhenius parameters for hydrolysis of di-*m*-toluidine phosphate at 60 °C

HCl (mol dm ⁻³)	<i>E</i> (kcal/mol)	<i>A</i> (s ⁻¹)	-Δ <i>S</i> [‡] (e.u.)
3.00	15.56	2.50 × 10 ¹⁰	21.17
5.00	15.10	2.68 × 10 ¹⁰	21.29

slope of the linear curve is *b*'_{H+}, which is equal to *b*'_{H+}/2.303 and intercept on log rate axis is 3 + log *k*_{H0+} (Fig. not shown).

The sum of neutral and acid rates agree well with the experimentally observed rates (Table 1) up to 5.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl. In the region of 0.1 to 5.0 mol dm⁻³ the rate law is calculated by equation :

$$k = 3.72 \times 10^{-3} \cdot C_{H^+} \exp(0.085 \times 2.303)\mu + 5.45 \times 10^{-3} \quad (3)$$

The lowering in rates in 6.0 and 7.0 mol dm⁻³ can be explained by considering water activity as an additional parameter represented as :

$$k = k_{H_0^+} \cdot C_{H^+} \exp b'_{H^+} \cdot \mu (a_{H_2O})^n + k_N \quad (4)$$

where *n* is an integer and (*a*_{H₂O})^{*n*} is water activity¹⁴. Hence the rate laws beyond 5.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl were calculated by employing Bronsted-Bjerrum equation¹⁵ :

$$k = 3.72 \times 10^{-3} \cdot C_{H^+} \exp(0.085 \times 2.303) \cdot \mu (a_{H_2O})^n + 5.45 \times 10^{-3} \quad (5)$$

The revised estimated rates now agree with the experimentally observed rates (Table 1).

sis at 3.0 and 5.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl (Table 2):

The magnitude of the Arrhenius parameters falls in the range of bimolecular reaction¹⁷. Bimolecular nature of reaction is further supported by plots of Hammett¹⁸ (0.52), Zucker-Hammett¹⁹ (1.01) and Bunnett (*w* = 7.18, *w** = 1.63). Bunnett-Olsen²⁰ parameter (*Φ* = 1.28 which is greater than 0.58) (plots not shown) suggested that water is involved as a proton transfer agent in the rate determining step.

The effect of concentration of diester on the rate of hydrolysis also confirms the order of reaction²¹ to be one with respect to the diester by reducing half (*k* = 55.54 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹) or double (*k* = 56.12 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹) the normal concentration (*k* = 55.22 × 10⁻³ min⁻¹) at 5.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl.

Di-*m*-toluidine phosphate may undergo hydrolysis either by P-N or C-N bond fission. Table 3 summarizes comparative rate data²² for the hydrolysis of other diesters studied kinetically shows isokinetic relationship²³. The point of di-*m*-toluidine phosphate lies on the linear curve of those diesters which are known to undergo hydrolysis via P-N bond fission (Fig. not shown). Thus P-N rather than C-N bond fission appears to be more probable.

Conclusions :

In the region 0.1 to 7.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl di-*m*-toluidine phosphate has been found to hydrolyze via neutral and conjugate acid species. The acid catalyzed hydrolysis is

Table 3. Comparative kinetic rate data for hydrolysis of some phosphate diesters via conjugate acid species

Sr. no.	Phosphate diesters	Medium HCl (mol dm ⁻³)	<i>E</i> (kcal/mol)	-Δ <i>S</i> [‡] (e.u.)	Molecularity	Fission
1.	Cyclohexyl amine phosphate	3.0	12.09	37.11	2	P-N
2.	<i>o</i> -Toluidine phosphate	1.0	11.40	38.66	2	P-N
3.	<i>p</i> -Phenatadine phosphate	3.0	5.72	70.55	2	P-N
4.	<i>p</i> -Nitro aniline phosphate	3.0	11.64	53.31	2	P-N
5.	<i>m</i> -Toluidine phosphate	3.0	15.56	21.29	2	Present work

Solvent effect (Table 1) shows a significant rise in rates, dioxane being a better proton donar than water, increases the concentration of conjugate acid species resulting in the increased rates. Effect on the rate of hydrolysis may, therefore, be taken to indicate the formation of transition state in which charge is dispersed and this is accordance with Chanley's observation¹⁶.

Arrhenius parameters are determined for the hydroly-

subjected to positive effect of ionic strength. Bimolecular nature of hydrolysis has been supported by different parameters such as Hammett, Zucker-Hammett, Bunnett, Bunnett-Olsen and Arrhenius etc. Comparative kinetic rate data of other diesters has supported the P-N bond fission.

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